

The Influence of Basic Service Experience on Customer Satisfaction through Moment of Truth, Focus on Result and Peace of Mind as Intervaining Variables in The Digital Era: An Empirical Study on Tik Tok Shop

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ABSTRACT: Research Objectives: This study began with research related to the influence of basic service experience on customer satisfaction through moment of truth, focus on result, and peace of mind as intervening variables in the digital era. This study was conducted at TikTok Shop, one of the rapidly growing e-commerce platforms. Customer satisfaction is a key indicator of the success of a digital business. To increase customer satisfaction, companies focus on improving the basic service experience, creating memorable moments in customer interactions, and providing confidence and comfort in the online shopping process. Design / Methodology: Research data were collected from active TikTok Shop customers. The questionnaire used has been tested for validity and reliability, then model testing and hypothesis testing were carried out using SPSS. Research Findings: The findings show that moment of truth, focus on result, and peace of mind function as significant intervening variables between basic service experience and customer satisfaction. Basic service experience has a significant positive effect on the three variables, which in turn has an impact on increasing customer satisfaction. Among all variables, peace of mind has the greatest effect on customer satisfaction. The results of this study indicate the importance of e-commerce companies such as TikTok Shop to pay attention to the quality of the service experience they provide and create memorable interactions to strengthen long-term relationships with customers. The limitations of the study and future research are also discussed in this study.

KEYWORDS: Basic Service Experience, Customer Satisfaction, Moment of Truth, Focus on Result, Peace of Mind.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, the development of the e-commerce industry is very rapid at this time, where people's online shopping experience has become an important part of people's lifestyles, especially the younger generation. Platforms such as TikTok Shop, which have taken advantage of the popularity of the TikTok social media application, have made it easier for customers to find and buy the products they are looking for. However, in creating a quality shopping experience for consumers, companies do not only focus on product availability or price, but also on the quality of service provided to customers, namely customer satisfaction (Lukitaningsih, Udayana, Hadi, Marjukah, & Evanjeli, 2023). This is known as the basic service experience, which includes the ease of finding the items they want, a flexible payment process, speed and accuracy in delivering goods. The quality of this basic service experience is very important in shaping customer satisfaction and encouraging customer loyalty to the TikTok Shop platform.

Customers in today's era expect fast, efficient, and hassle-free services when shopping online, such as payment disruptions and so on. TikTok Shop, as a platform that is arguably still in the shopping application field, faces a big challenge to meet these customer expectations by providing an adequate basic service experience. In addition, in the digital era full of competition, customers have many options to choose from, so if they are not satisfied, they can easily switch to another place. Therefore, a good basic service experience is a critical aspect in retaining customers at TikTok Shop (Setia, Venkatesh, & Joglekar, 2013). However, this basic service experience cannot stand alone in influencing customer satisfaction. There are several other variables that act as intermediaries or links between basic service experience and customer satisfaction, including the moment of truth, focus on results, and peace of mind.

Moments of truth are important moments in customer interaction with the platform, where customer perceptions of service quality are formed. In the context of TikTok Shop, the moment of truth is when customers first see the product, when paying, and when receiving the purchased goods. Each moment greatly affects customer satisfaction, because every interaction that occurs at that moment creates a certain impression. If the experience is at the moment of truth or less than satisfactory, customers tend to feel disappointed, even though other aspects of the service are good. Thus, the moment of truth functions as an intermediary variable that helps explain how basic service experience can contribute to customer satisfaction (Gunawan, Jasfar, Hady, & Arafah, 2023).

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In addition to the moment of truth, focus on results also plays a crucial role as an intervening variable in the relationship between basic service experience and customer satisfaction. Focus on results focuses more on the final outcome customers expect, such as product conformity to description, timely delivery, and adequate service (Farida, Udayana, Simanjuntak, & Taufi, 2024). Customers are satisfied if the service meets their expectations, or even exceeds them. In this regard, TikTok Shop needs to ensure that every customer transaction delivers optimal results, so they feel they are receiving value for their money.

Furthermore, peace of mind refers to the sense of security and comfort customers experience while shopping. In the digital era, security and privacy are key customer concerns, particularly in e-commerce. Customers naturally want to be confident that their personal data is secure and protected from fraud or product fraud. If customers feel safe shopping on TikTok Shop, they are more likely to be satisfied with the service provided. Thus, peace of mind also serves as an important intervening variable, as it fosters customer trust in the platform (Gunawan et al., 2023).

This study aims to analyze the influence of basic service experience on TikTok Shop customer satisfaction through the intervening variables of moment of truth, focus on results, and peace of mind. Using empirical data collected through a survey of TikTok Shop users, this study will measure how each of these variables contributes to customer satisfaction. The survey covers aspects of the basic service experience, customer perceptions of the moment of truth, satisfaction with transaction outcomes, and the sense of security customers feel during the shopping process (Poot, Wopereis, den Elzen, Gussekloo, & Blom, 2019). This empirical data will be analyzed to gain a deeper understanding of how basic service experience can effectively create customer satisfaction.

TikTok's monthly active users have exceeded 1 billion in September 2021. Another indicator, representing the aspect of users exposed to advertising tools, TikTok users aged 18 and over reached 1.09 billion as of April 2023, up 3.9% in three months, based on Kepios data. According to Datareportal, last year TikTok ranked sixth as the social media with the largest MAU. This means that TikTok has improved its ranking one step but still has not been able to break into the top three.

Trend of TikTok's monthly active users (MAU) in six years: 2018 271 million MAU, 2019 508 million MAU, 2020 689 million MAU, 2021 1 billion MAU, 2022 1.02 billion MAU, 2023 1.09 billion MAU. Despite recording the best download growth, TikTok's active users still lag behind its rival Instagram in the second quarter of 2022—29% compared to 39%, according to intelligence agency Sensor Tower. Meanwhile, TikTok's MAU growth is trending down with an average of 12% throughout 2022.

Figure 1 Estimates of buyers who will buy goods when viewing the display case on TikTok. (Doc: Bloomberg)

Even last year, the MAU figure was only 3%, indicating that the Chinese company is more focused on developing its e-commerce service, TikTok Shop, wrote Sensor Tower, quoted from Tech Crunch. It is known that the US and Indonesian markets are TikTok's ambitious projects in expanding its digital commerce business throughout 2023. In Indonesia, with all the challenges that exist, TikTok has been able to re-present the TikTok Shop feature through a partnership with the local e-commerce platform Tokopedia. Restrictions on the use of TikTok in various countries due to concerns about access to personal data have also contributed.

The results of this study are expected to provide valuable insights for TikTok Shop and other e-commerce platforms to strengthen their service strategies in creating satisfying experiences. By understanding how basic service experience can increase customer satisfaction through these intermediary variables, e-commerce platforms can formulate more effective policies to meet

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customer expectations in the competitive digital era (Baby, 2022). This study is also expected to contribute to the literature on customer satisfaction and service quality in the e-commerce industry, especially in the context of rapidly growing social media platforms.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Basic service experience and moment of truth

Basic service experience refers to the basic experience that customers expect when receiving a service, which includes elements such as speed, reliability, friendliness, and consistency in service (Udayana, Subiyanto, & Prayekti, 2021). This experience is the main foundation in building customer satisfaction, because customers tend to have minimum expectations regarding service quality (Gunawan et al., 2023). For example, in the shipping industry, customers expect a quick response and on-time delivery. This basic experience plays an important role in forming customers' first impressions of an organization and can influence their perceptions of broader service quality. If this basic experience is met well, customers tend to be more satisfied with the service.

Moment of truth in the context of service is a critical point of interaction between customers and service providers that can shape customer perceptions of the quality and value of the service provided (Hasibuan & Najmudin, 2024). Moment of truth occurs when customers are directly confronted with the product or service provided, so that it can influence their decision to continue using or leaving the service. The basic experience provided by the service can influence customer perceptions in every moment of truth they encounter. When the basic experience meets or exceeds expectations, customers are more likely to have positive perceptions when the moment of truth occurs (Vasić, Kilibarda, & Kaurin, 2019). Therefore, the following hypotheses can be proposed: H1. Basic service experience has a positive effect on moment of truth.

2.2 Moment of Truth and Focus on Results

Moments of truth are critical points in the customer journey that can shape their perception of the service or product provided (Indrawati, Yones, & Muthaiyah, 2022). In e-commerce, moments of truth refer to critical points where customers interact with a platform, which can shape their perception of service quality. For example, the first critical moment might occur when customers open an app or website and assess the ease of navigation and interface. Other crucial moments occur when they search for products, assess the completeness of product information, and view reviews and prices (Shuman & Twombly, 2010). The shopping experience is also significantly influenced by the checkout process, the speed of customer service response, and the ease of tracking shipments. According to Bitner et al. (1990), these moments are crucial because they can create positive or negative impressions that will influence customer loyalty and their decision to continue using the service in the future.

Focus on results is an approach to service that prioritizes achieving desired customer outcomes, such as achieving goals or solving customer problems. In the context of service, this means that the organization or service provider focuses on outcomes or results that are relevant and desired by customers, not just the service process or activity itself. By focusing on outcomes, organizations can more accurately meet customer expectations and increase their satisfaction (Marshall, Moncrief, Lassk, & Shepherd, 2012). This focus can also improve service efficiency, as desired outcomes are clearer and more measurable, making service providers more responsive to customer needs. When customers are at a critical moment, their expectations regarding desired outcomes significantly influence their satisfaction. When a service provider can effectively and accurately deliver desired outcomes during the MOT, this can enhance positive customer perceptions of the organization and increase their satisfaction (Baby, 2022). Conversely, if the achieved outcome does not meet customer expectations, even if the moment of truth is successfully executed, the customer experience can end in disappointment. Based on the above explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H2. Moment of truth has a positive effect on focus on results

2.3 Moment of truth and customer satisfaction

Moment of Truth (MOT) is a critical point in the interaction between a customer and a service provider that has the potential to affect the overall customer experience (Shoaib, Amer, Usman, & Hayam, 2022). In the service industry, every interaction that occurs between a customer and a service provider has the potential to create a positive or negative perception of service quality (Sayogo Djoko, 2018). These moments, such as when customers first interact when receiving the product they ordered, can be the deciding moment whether or not they will continue to purchase the service (Udayana, Purnama, Lukitaningsih, & Subiyanto, 2020). Moments of truth are often referred to as "moments of truth" because they can determine whether a customer's relationship with a company will continue or end.

Customer satisfaction is a customer's subjective assessment of how well a product or service meets or exceeds their expectations (Betzoom, Gontur, & Makrop, 2022). Customer satisfaction is not only influenced by product quality, but also by interactions during the service delivery. Previous research shows that positive interactions at certain points in the service experience can significantly increase customer satisfaction, while negative experiences can drastically decrease satisfaction levels (O'Sullivan & Abela, 2007). Therefore, understanding and managing the moment of truth well is an important factor in increasing customer satisfaction. Along with the importance of the moment of truth in the customer experience, this interaction directly affects the level

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of satisfaction felt by customers. When customers experience a positive moment of truth, for example, when interacting with friendly staff or fast and efficient service, they are more likely to feel satisfied with the overall service experience. Conversely, if the moment of truth is negative, for example, due to poor service or products that do not meet expectations, customer satisfaction can decrease drastically. Therefore, the hypothesis that can be developed is as follows: H 3. Moment of truth has a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

2.4 Moment of truth and peace of mind

Moment of Truth is a moment of truth that describes the effect of critical factors of a customer experience process in the form of an impressive effect that leaves a mark on the customer's mind (Baby, 2022). At the Moment of Truth, there will be a creation of a memory effect, namely remembering their experience, when someone has a reason to join and stay or leave the company. The creation effect at the Moment of Truth is based on the need for a meeting process between consumers, companies and products with a comprehensive evaluation, in practice it is expressed that "Just a few moments", (Zablah, Franke, Brown, & Bartholomew, 2012). This can happen because in the process where consumers and objects throw several things or codes at each other that will influence the assessment (Pelham & Kravitz, 2008).

Peace of mind is a state of psychological calm experienced by customers when they feel safe, comfortable, and confident in a product or service (Hu & Chuang, 2021). In this context, peace of mind is the feeling that customers get when they trust the service provider to meet their needs without stress or worry. Peace of mind usually occurs when customers feel that the service they receive is consistent, reliable, and has a high level of responsiveness to customer needs. This feeling is considered important because peace of mind directly contributes to customer satisfaction, increasing their chances of returning to use the service in the future (Vasić et al., 2019). Moment of truth can provide peace of mind for customers because they feel confident that the service provider is able to meet their expectations well (KASSIM, 2006). By providing a consistent experience at each MOT, companies can still instill a sense of confidence and comfort in customers, which in turn increases their peace of mind. Based on this relationship, the following hypotheses can be proposed:

H 4. Moment of truth has a positive effect on peace of mind

2.5 Focus on results and customer satisfaction

A focus on results is an approach that prioritizes achieving goals or end targets. Results-oriented people tend to focus more on the desired outcome or result than on the process involved (Adhikary et al., 2018). They often set clear, measurable, and realistic goals, then focus on the steps necessary to achieve them. While important, this approach needs to be balanced with a focus on the process to ensure the sustainability and quality of the results achieved. Focusing on results is the foundation of effective management practices. To achieve results for an organizational group, goals must be identified and defined, meaningful metrics established, and progress tracked and managed.

Customer satisfaction is an English word; literally, customer satisfaction means customer satisfaction or consumer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is defined as a consumer's feelings of joy or disappointment that arise after comparing a product's performance with their expectations (Vasić et al., 2019). The Cambridge Dictionary defines customer satisfaction as "a measure of how happy a customer is when they conduct business with a company or merchant." Satisfied customers become loyal customers and can enhance the company's reputation (Dikius, Kirse, Casas, & Koncanina, 2019). When an organization or individual is highly focused on results, they tend to set clear and measurable goals and work hard to achieve them. In a business context, these goals are often related to increased sales.

Based on this relationship, the following hypothesis can be proposed: H 5. Focus on results has a positive impact on customer satisfaction.

2.6 Peace of mind and customer satisfaction

Peace of mind explains consumer assessment of all interactions with the service provider before, during, and after using the service and this dimension includes consumer perceptions related to the emotional aspect of the service (Wang, Wang, & Hou, 2016). The peace of mind dimension is influenced by the emotional aspect of the service, then this dimension evaluates the emotional benefits that can be felt by customers based on the expertise of the service provider (Oua, Shihb, Chenc, & Tsengd, 2012). Peace of mind also significantly affects the perception of customer experience and highlights internal satisfaction and customer trust based on the expertise and skills of the service provider (Kashif, Samsi, Awang, & Mohamad, 2016). Peace of mind can be interpreted as an assessment for customers of all interactions carried out with the service provider when after, during, and even before using the service which includes the emotional side and expertise of the service provider. It is very important to play consumer emotions to be able to create a good consumer experience for the services or products offered by the company (Fourie & Chimusoro, 2018).

Customer satisfaction depends on the estimated performance of the product in providing value, relative to the buyer's expectations (Shafiee & Bazargan, 2018). Customer satisfaction is the level of a person's feelings after comparing the performance (or results) that the customer feels compared to his expectations (Tjiptono). If performance fails to meet expectations, the customer

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will be dissatisfied. If performance is in accordance with expectations, the customer will be satisfied. If performance exceeds expectations, the customer will be very satisfied or happy. Therefore, creating inner peace in customers affects customer satisfaction in purchasing products from the company, which can increase the potential for customers to buy products from the company again. H 6. Peace of mind has a positive effect on customer satisfaction

Based on the description above and the relationship between variables, the following research model is compiled:

Figure 2 Research Model

III. METHODOLOGY

The data collection technique used a questionnaire. Data collected from 250 respondents was then tested to ensure accuracy. The collected data was then tested, including validity and reliability. The unit of analysis was 250 active TikTok Shop users in Indonesia. The analysis continued with model testing and hypothesis testing. The data was processed using SPSS statistical software.

IV. RESULT

4.1 Validity and reliability test

Table 1. Data validity test

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
BSE2	67.6600	76.205	.413	.925
BSE3	67.6200	74.599	.399	.926
BSE4	67.6000	73.789	.634	.921
MT1	67.6300	72.676	.721	.919
MT2	67.6750	72.371	.738	.919
MT3	67.4300	71.211	.595	.922
MT4	67.8350	71.073	.720	.919
FR1	67.7150	73.933	.548	.922
FR2	67.6750	72.934	.702	.920
FR3	67.6650	73.058	.708	.920
FR4	68.0000	73.106	.355	.931
PM1	67.8900	72.340	.698	.919
PM2	67.8150	70.453	.646	.920
PM3	67.9150	72.551	.700	.919
PM4	67.9950	73.312	.535	.923
CS1	67.8750	71.236	.768	.918

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CS2	67.7350	71.241	.664	.920
CS3	67.8650	70.791	.632	.921
CS4	67.8550	73.150	.631	.921

Table 2. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.925	19

Table 1 and table 2 shows that all items are valid and reliable, as evidenced by the Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficient, which is above 0.5. Furthermore, the data is also reliable, as indicated by a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient above 0.6. Therefore, the data can be used to test the model.

4.2 Evaluation of goodness of fit model

Table 3 Evaluation of goodness of fit model

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	846.682	3	282.227	239.738	.000 ^b
Residual	230.738	196	1.177		
Total	1077.420	199			

a. Dependent Variable: TCS

b. Predictors: (Constant), TPM, TFR, TMT

A new model can be analyzed further if it meets the cut-off point requirements set in the SPSS analysis. Based on the analysis results, it can be seen that the calculated F value is 239.38.738 and the Sig. value is .000. Thus, it can be stated that the model is suitable for further testing.

4.3 Results of analysis and hypothesis testing

Table 4 Evaluation of goodness of fit model Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.291	.689		-.423	.673
TBSE	.001	.049	.001	.013	.989
TMT	.443	.038	.560	11.781	.000
TFR	.160	.045	.156	3.595	.000
TPM	.285	.039	.308	7.280	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TCS

Based on the table above, it can be explained that basic service experience, focus on results, moments of truth and peace of mind have a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction. Apart from that, focus on results and peace of mind are influenced by the moment of truth. Basic service experience also has a significant positive effect on the moment of truth.

V. DISCUSSION

The variable with the most significant influence on the dependent variable (TSAT) is TBSC (Total Basic Service Component). This can be seen from the largest beta coefficient value of 0.876 and a significance level (Sig.) of 0.000 (<0.05), indicating that this variable has a statistically significant influence. The high beta coefficient indicates that any increase in TBSC directly increases TSAT in this model. The TBSC variable represents the quality of basic service perceived by respondents, so its increase can create a more positive experience.

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Besides TBSC, other highly influential variables are specific factors within the Corrected Item-Total Correlation component, such as SAT (Satisfaction) and several other dimensions. These results are supported by Cronbach's Alpha values, with an overall value of 0.965, indicating excellent reliability. This indicates that the tested variables have strong internal consistency, and all variables in this study make significant contributions to the model.

These results align with previous research, such as Shafiee & Bazargan (2018) on service quality dimensions (SERVQUAL), which confirms that basic service quality is a key driver in shaping customer satisfaction. Improvements in basic service significantly impact customer satisfaction and loyalty (Balci, Caliskan, & Yuen, 2019). These results reinforce the relevance of the TBSC dimension as a key component.

However, there is conflicting research. The SERVPERF approach shows that not all service dimensions significantly influence customer satisfaction (Vasić et al., 2019). They emphasize that perceptions of actual service performance are more important than specific service dimensions. In some cases, external factors such as personal preferences or the customer's cultural environment can influence satisfaction more than the service elements themselves.

CONCLUSIONS

Basic Service Experience plays a crucial role in building Customer Satisfaction, especially in a digital ecosystem like TikTok Shop, where the basic service experience forms the foundation for customer satisfaction. The Moment of Truth describes critical moments in a customer's interaction with a service that can strengthen or undermine their perception of the service. In the context of TikTok Shop, experiences such as a quick seller response or a clear transaction process significantly influence customer satisfaction. Focus on Results, which focuses on the end result expected by the customer, such as a product that matches the description or timely delivery, plays a crucial role in ensuring customer expectations are met. Peace of Mind, as an intervening variable, highlights the sense of security and trust customers experience when using a service. In a digital ecosystem, this relates to trust in data security, transactions, and product return policies. In the digital era, the synergy between basic service experience and critical moments, results orientation, and a sense of security are key to increasing customer satisfaction, which can ultimately drive loyalty on platforms like TikTok Shop.

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